

Influence of Students' Entry Behavior on History and Government Curriculum Implementation in Kenya: A Study across Secondary Schools in Emuhaya Sub County

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ABSTRACT: There had been a growing concern among educators and other stakeholders on the successful implementation of the History and Government curriculum. Data on students' performance in History and Government at secondary school level indicated that the implementation of the curriculum was not as envisaged. Thus statistics of Kenya Certificate of Secondary School Examination (KCSE) of 2019 revealed that 69.13% of candidates in Kenya took history and government in 2019 KCSE examinations and the mean score of the subjects nationally was 4.1 which is a D+ according to the grading system. Students' performance in Emuhaya Sub-county had been low for the years from 2016 to 2019 where performance was; 3.59 lower than the neighbouring sub-counties, that is Hamisi, 5.33; Vihiga, 4.72; Sabatia, 5.12 and Luanda, 4.25 Sub-Counties. The objective of the study was to determine the influence of students' entry behavior on the successful implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Secondary schools in Emuhaya Sub County, Kenya. A conceptual framework postulating the influence of the students' entry behavior (Independent Variable) on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum (Dependent Variable) was used to focus on the objective of the study. The findings of the study indicated that students' entry behaviour accounted for 13.7% of KCSE History and Government mean score. This means that the students' entry behavior contributed for 13.7% to the successful implementation of History and Government in secondary schools. 86.3% was the contribution made by other factors that were not subject of the study. These factors included teaching learning resources, teachers' qualifications, school infrastructure, teachers' attitudes among others. The study concluded that the entry behavior of students significantly influenced the successful implementation of History and Government curriculum at secondary school level. The findings of this study are significant to the Ministry of Education and School Boards of Management in formulation of policies that can enhance implementation of History and Government Curriculum. The findings also form baseline information for further studies in related areas.

KEY WORDS: Curriculum Implementation Kenya: Secondary Schools, Emuhaya Sub County, Influence, Students' Entry Behavior, History and Government.

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum, as defined by UNESCO (2013), is a framework that sets the subjects, time frame, specific material, teaching-learning methodologies to be implemented to influence core values, and assessment criteria. A comprehensive categorization of curriculum encompasses non-formal curriculum, which pertains to any structured educational endeavor functioning beyond the confines of the formal system. Informal education is a continuous and ongoing process in which individuals gain attitudes, skills, and information via their daily experiences. Lastly we have formal curriculum whereby education is generally offered by qualified teachers in a systematic planned fashion within a school, higher education or university. In Kenya formal curriculum is employed in schools.

According to Jarolimek, (1971), as reported in Nasibi (2015), Dr. Arnold of the Rugby School was the first person to seriously investigate History at the elementary school level in 1853. Twenty years later, in 1872-74, it was offered in post-primary schools, and by 1881, history had a thoroughly developed syllabus and was a completely accepted optional subject. History should be taught in schools, according to many educators, since it helps pupils identify with the rich historical context and helps to strengthen allegiances. Others have claimed that history's distinctive contribution to the curriculum is due to its precise interest in the notion of continuity and transformation, according to Batho (1985), as cited in Nasibi (2015). Others see it as a light that enlightens people's life because "those who are blind to or ignorant of their past are likewise blind of their future," despite the fact that "it is concerned

with the reconstruction of the past." For many years, Americans have viewed studying history as a goal in and of itself. Political instruction (civics) instruction about history and development has long been defended as a practice that would create better citizens. According to Rothsten (2004), this makes it difficult to teach history.

African history was viewed as a continuation of European history because it began with the arrival of Europeans (Hansen & Jonsson, 2014). The western educational system developed in Africa and worldwide was used to spread these viewpoints. According to Were (1967), "throughout my work, I realized that nearly all the history taught was foreign and comprised mostly of the period of European domination. In schools, no African history was taught. African historians provided evidence that the continent had a past before the arrival of the Europeans. For instance, according to Ajaego (1990), "African societies had formed a vast history and culture before the emergence of written culture." The educational system in Kenya has undergone two major changes. The current educational system, which is based on the 8-4-4 system, which has undergone two revisions in 1992 and 2002, is different from the older 7-4-2-3 system. Before 1986, secondary school history classes covered a wide range of topics, including world history in the first and second grades, history of East Africa and Kenya in the third and fourth grades, and any two African regions. But just as in any other nation, politics heavily impact Kenya's educational system. The Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development Act No.4 of 2013 of Kenyan Legislation created the national curriculum development center known as the Kenyan Institute of Education (Republic of Kenya, 2013). However, Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development was established to pursue the following objectives: develop research-informed curricula and curriculum support materials for basic and tertiary education and training outside of universities; implement policies relating to curriculum development in basic and tertiary education and training; initiate and carry out research to inform curriculum policies; review and development; print, publish, and disseminate information relating to basic and tertiary education and training curricula; provide advisory services for basic and post-secondary education and training.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE ON INFLUENCE OF STUDENTS' ENTRY BEHAVIOR ON HISTORY AND GOVERNMENT CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION

The entry behavior of students in secondary school is the marks with which the learners transit from primary school to secondary school. Njagi (2018) in the study titled: Factors influencing provision of quality education in newly established secondary schools in Mathira Constituency, Kenya. One of the objectives was to analyze the entry behavior of students in the newly established secondary schools in Mathira constituency, Kenya. The finding was that, the newly established secondary schools' entry behavior for learners was below the average marks of 250 in the KCPE examination. While discussing the literature review related to entry behavior, the study cited Sekyere, Sekyere and Akpalu (2013) whose study in Ghana had found that learners' entry behavior affected overall academic performance such that learners with high entry behavior exhibited higher academic achievement. The reviewed study did not indicate method used to collect data, method used to analyze data and sample size used, it do not assertively indicate the fact that entry behavior influences academic performance and particularly with respect to History and Government.

Simatwa, Khajeha and Baraza (2019a) in their study titled; Influence of students' entry behaviour on academic achievement in National polytechnics in Kenya. The study adopted descriptive and co-relational research designs. The study population was 645 students, 41 lecturers, 1 librarian, 3 technicians and 1 principal. Simple random sampling was used to select 241 students and 37 lecturers while 1 principal, 3 technicians and 1 librarian were selected by saturated sampling. Questionnaires, interviews and document analysis guide were used to collect data. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means and regression analysis. The objective of the study was to determine influence of students' entry behavior on academic achievement on engineering courses in National polytechnic in Kenya. The finding was that, students' entry behaviour accounted for 6.3% of the variation in students' academic achievement in engineering courses therefore Students' entry behavior influences students' academic achievement in polytechnics in Kenya. The reviewed study does not indicate the extent to which students entry behavior affects implementation of History and Government curriculum in secondary school, instead it only indicate how it influences engineering courses in national polytechnics.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: A Conceptual framework showing the Influence of Students’ Entry Behavior on the Implementation of History and Government Curriculum.

The study examined the influence of students’ entry behavior on the implementation of History and Government curriculum in Emuhaya Sub-County. Student entry behavior means the prerequisite knowledge, attitude and skills which the students already possess that are relevant to the learning task or subject matter and that you may require student to demonstrate before beginning to attend at secondary school level. In this case, the students’ entry behavior was the students’ performance at KCPE level which is the primary education cycle. KCSE is the summative examination that is administered to students who have completed the secondary education cycle. This forms the entry behavior to tertiary education. In this conceptual framework it was hypothesized that students’ entry behavior influenced the successful implementation of the history and Government curriculum. The intervening variables are moderating or confounding factors which included student teacher ratio and parental influence.

Research Objective

The research objective was to determine influence of students’ entry behavior on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Secondary Schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research adopted descriptive survey and correlation research designs. The target population consisted of 1 County Quality Standards Assurance Officer, 2 Curriculum Support Officers, 31 Principals, 64 History and Government teachers and 1,125 form three History and Government students totaling to 1223. The sample size consisted of 22 Principals, 2 Curriculum Support Officer, 55 History and Government teachers and 286 KCSE 2020 History and Government students. Simple random sampling was used to select 55 teachers and 286 form three History and Government students. The County Quality Assurance Officer, 2 Curriculum Support Officers and 22 principals were purposively selected for the study hence 366 respondents. Data collection instruments included questionnaires, interview schedules and observations. Validity of the instruments was ascertained by three experts from the department by examining the instruments and incorporating their input. Reliability of instruments was done by piloting in 9 schools and test and re-test method was used to determine reliability where Pearson’s (r) coefficient of 0.7 and above calculated at p- value of 0.05 was considered reliable. The reliability coefficient for teachers questionnaire was 0.78 and 0.8 for students

questionnaire. Data was analyzed by use of descriptive statistics, that is, frequency counts, percentages and means. Inferential statistics, that is, regression analysis was used to determine the influence.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Category of Respondents		Frequency	Percent
Students	Male	131	45.8
	Female	155	54.2
	Total	286	100.0
Teachers	Male	22	40.0
	Female	33	60.0
	Total	55	100.0

Table 1 illustrates that females constitute a higher percentage (54.2%) in terms of History and Government students compared to Males (45.8%). However, female (60%) teachers of History and Government constitute the majority compared to males (40%). The representation of respondents was good for balanced responses based on gender.

Table 2: Teaching Experience

Teaching experience in Years	Frequency	Percentage
1	0	0
2	13	23.6
3	6	11
4	8	14.5
5	16	29
6	3	5.5
7	0	0
8	3	5.5
9	0	0
10	6	11
Total	55	100

From Table 2 it can be noted that majority of instructors 16 (4.7%) had a teaching experience of five years. The data exposed that a bigger percentage of teachers had an experience of five years and above hence were in a good position to answer questions regarding on the implementation of History and Government curriculum. That data also shows that no teacher had less than one year teaching experience.

Table 3: Academic Qualification of Teachers

Highest Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Bachelors of degree	55	100
Total	55	100

From Table 3, it can be noted that all the teachers had a Bachelor’s of Education degree. This depicts that the instructors engaged in the study were adequately qualified to teach and hence they were in a better position to give a comprehensive view on the status of History and Government curriculum implementation.

Table 4: Other Teaching Subjects

Subject	Frequency	Percent
Christian Religious Education	24	43.6
Geography	9	16.4
Kiswahili	22	40
Total	55	100

Table 4 reveals that majority (43.6%) of History and Government teachers taught CRE as well. It is also noteworthy that a considerable number of history and government teachers combined it with Kiswahili as well. This was important to understand other commitments of the teachers and establish whether the variation in implementation of History and Government curriculum could be accredited to the divided attention to the other subjects.

Table 5: Seminars Attended

Seminar attendance	Frequency	Percent
Termly	34	61.8
Yearly	18	32.7
Total	52	94.5

Data in Table 5 indicates that majority of the teachers (61.8%) attended seminars termly and that only a few (32.7%) attended yearly. This shows that the teachers are constantly updated on the dynamics in the history and government curriculum and thus are required to implement it smoothly. This was important to this study as it shows the progress made to ensure that the curriculum is realized. The information teachers obtain from equipped teachers with skills and knowledge that helped them to respond to questions regarding History and Government implementation.

Research Objective

The research objective was to determine influence of entry behavior of students on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Secondary Schools. Data on performance of students in KCPE for the 2016 cohort was obtained from the principals of respective schools. The data obtained was analysed and presented as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Students’ Performance in Social Studies in Kenya Certificate of Primary Education for the 2016 cohort

12-Point Grade	Grade	Frequency	Percentage
1	E	0	0
2	D-	7	2.4
3	D	19	6.6
4	D+	23	8
5	C-	32	11.2
6	C	41	14.3
7	C+	35	12.2
8	B-	31	10.8
9	B	31	10.8
10	B+	36	12.6
11	A-	17	5.9
12	A	14	4.9
Mean			7.19

From Table 6 majority 41(14.3%) of the learners under study scored an aggregate of 6 points which was the average point out of the possible 12 points. It is clear from the data analysis that majority of the students performed well in Social Studies which is a prerequisite of selecting History and Government as a subject of study in secondary schools.

Data on students’ performance of the 2016 KCPE cohort that progressed to secondary schools and pursued History and Government was analysed and the results were as presented in Table 7.

Note: the 2020 KCSE cohort of students who came from the 2016 KCPE cohort

Table 7: Students’ Performance in KCSE in History and Government for the 2020 Cohort.

12-Point Grade	Grade	Frequency	Percentage
1	E	0	0
2	D-	8	2.8
3	D	23	8.0
4	D+	11	3.8
5	C-	38	13.3
6	C	36	12.6
7	C+	37	13.0
8	B-	38	13.3
9	B	22	7.7
10	B+	33	11.5
11	A-	28	9.8
12	A	12	4.2
Mean			7.27

From Table 7, majority of the students obtained between 6 and 12 points in History and Government in their KCSE examinations. This implies that the students’ performance in KCSE examinations in History and Government were consistent with their performance in KCPE in 2016. It also means that in terms of entry behavior the variance was minimum but progressive. For instance no candidate scored 1 point in KCSE and KCPE cohorts. The general trend is more or less the same with very minimal variations.

To estimate influence of students’ entry behavior on curriculum implementation in History and Government regression analysis was computed. Thus, the 2016 cohort KCPE results with the 2020 cohort KCSE results were used in the computation and the results were as shown in Table 8. The 2016 and 2020 cohort consisted of 2020 students who did the KCPE in 2016 and KCSE in 2020 and therefore were appropriate in establishing the influence of entry behavior on History and Government curriculum implementation.

Table 8. Regression analysis on the influence of Entry Behaviour on the Implementation of History and Government Curriculum

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.374 ^a	.140	.137	2.388	.140	46.176	1	284	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students entry behavior

Regression analysis (Table 8) revealed that students’ entry behavior had significant influence on History and Government curriculum implementation at secondary school level. This is because the adjusted R² coefficient was 0.137 at the p-value of 0.000 which was less than the set p-value of 0.05. Consequently, it can be noted that students’ entry behaviour accounted for 13.7% of the variation in learners’ scores as signified by the Adjusted R² coefficient of 0.137. This means that the other 86.3% was due to other factors such as infrastructure in the primary schools, parent’s social economic status and teachers’ motivation which were not the subject of this study.

To determine as to whether students entry behavior was a significant predictor of History and Government curriculum implementation, analysis of variance was computed and the results were as shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Analysis of Variance on Influence of Students Entry Behaviour on History and Government curriculum implementation

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	263.353	1	263.353	46.176	.000 ^b
	Residual	1619.724	284	5.703		
	Total	1883.077	285			

a. Dependent Variable: History and Government curriculum implementation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Students entry behavior

From Table 9 it can be observed that students’ entry behavior was established as a factor that was a predictor of implementation of History and Government curriculum. This was signified by the F – ratio ($F(1,284) = 0.000, P < 0.05$). This means that students’ entry behavior can be used to predict or determine the successful implementation of the History and Government curriculum in secondary schools.

To confirm the extent to which entry behavior can be used to determine the successful implementation of the History and Government curriculum, linear regression analysis was computed and the results were as shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Linear Regression Analysis of the Influence of Students’ Entry Behaviour on the implementation of History and Government Curriculum in Secondary Schools

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.797	.712		3.929	.000
	KCPE Social Studies scores	.482	.071	.374	6.795	.000

a. Dependent Variable : History and Government Curriculum Implementation

$$\text{Regression Equation } Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1$$

Table 10 shows that students’ entry behavior has a significant influence on the implementation of History and Government curriculum. That is, for every 1 unit increase in students’ entry behavior, there will be 0.482 units in History and Government curriculum implementation as signified by the coefficient 0.482. The regression model therefore is $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1$.

DISCUSSION

The findings of McDowell and Klattenberg (2019) observed that there was a growing emphasis on the need for an increased number of male teachers in educational conversations. Therefore, the researcher asserted that it was imperative to allocate sufficient attention to gender equality during the recruitment process of teachers.

The average mean score in KCSE (7.27) indicated above average performance (C+) which was desirable considering the good performance in their KCPE performance. Most schools preferred to use history and government as a booster subject for the overall mean grade of students so that they achieve the minimum overall grade besides the individual subject grade requirement for specific degree programmes. This degree programmes first requirement is that they should have a mean score of C+ and above. Hence as a booster it enables them to achieve this basic requirement. The varied degree programme such as Bachelor of Medicine and Surgery, Bachelor of Education, Bachelor of Science, Bachelor of Commerce, Bachelor of Law, Bachelor of Engineering among other degree programmes therefore are indirect beneficiaries of the implementation successful history and government curriculum. Social Studies as a discipline at primary school level is considered as the entry behavior of students into History and Government curriculum at secondary school level. Consequently the marks scored in Social Studies in KCPE by students, had a significant influence on their History and Government curriculum implementation performance in KCSE. The findings therefore indicated that students’ entry behaviour influenced the implementation of History curriculum. This was statistically significant since the p-value was <0.05. This implied that students’ entry behaviour influences History and Government curriculum implementation. In this case students’ entry behavior can be relied upon to predict successful implementation of History and Government curriculum.

Interview findings concurred with the questionnaire finding. Thus the Curriculum Support Officer stated that, even though History and Government is not taught as a stand alone subject, It is majorly associated with Social Studies and Religious Education in Primary school. It is worth noting that majority of the students who score well in Social Studies and Religious Education end up taking History and Government to completion and they do post above average performance. Interview with the County Quality and Assurance Standards Officer also concurred with these findings as he stated that, the implementation of the history and Government curriculum has everything to do with the type of students taking it. Most students undertaking History and Government up to form four have a history of scoring well in Social Studies and Religious Education (SSRE) in KCPE. He emphasized students who score well in SSRE and end up scoring poorly in KCSE but overall, they do post good results depending on how good their performance was in SSRE in primary school. Social Studies and Religious Education has a History studies component and this really prepares the student to pursue History and Government and the prospectus careers facilitated by such.”

The findings of this study concur with studies that were conducted in Ghana about learners’ entry behaviour and in Kenya in engineering course in national polytechnics. Sekyere, Sekyere and Akpalu (2013) whose study in Ghana had found that learners’ entry behavior affected overall academic performance such that learners with high entry behavior exhibited higher academic achievement. The reviewed study did not indicate the method used to collect data, the method used to analyze data and the sample size used, it does not assertively indicate the fact that entry behavior influences academic performance and particularly with respect to History and Government.

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CONCLUSION

The study concluded that students’ entry behavior significantly influences implementation of History and Government curriculum. This is important because it is the students who are the primary beneficiary of the curriculum and therefore it must be underscored in any other curriculum implementation at different levels.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i) The Ministry of Education should come up with a policy that affirms the fact that students’ entry behavior must be considered in the successful implementation of History and Government curriculum.
- ii) Students who have weak entry behavior should have their weaknesses diagnosed so as to help in implementation of the History and Government curriculum as desired.
- iii) For students who have weak entry behavior but have passion for History and Government curriculum, guidance and counseling services should be provided to them in order to help them understand the justification for inclusion and exclusion of students in the History and Government curriculum.
- iv) The school management should endeavor to provide the necessary prerequisite materials and human resource for successful implementation of History and Government curriculum.
- v) There is no single factor that can be relied upon for successful implementation of History and Government curriculum.

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